

Part-II: Information Analysis and Presentation: The Art of Academic Writing

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As I have discussed in the previous issue about constrains in preparing a viable research study, which was basically a theoretical discourse presumed to be of little effect in practice in devising suitable project for a study. As such, it seems to be my duty to discuss them sequentially.

Problem Identification or Selection of Topic: This is the first step towards the journey. Here the researcher must have a clear idea of

- (a) What he is doing and
- (b) Why?

That is,

- (i) The purpose and
- (ii) Relevancy of the work.

For example, for a study to assess the state-of-the-art research on Public Health and to identify the priority areas of Public Health Research for one's M.Phil. dissertation in LIS, the selected topic is something like: ***Bibliometric Analysis of Public Health Research***. Now, there are two underlying issues

- (a) A time limit for submission of the dissertation and
- (b) Selection of a topic *befitting* for the degree.

It is needless to say that the topic is too generalized or broad to manage. To make it manageable, some limiting factors were added and the topic thus modified to ***Bibliometric Analysis of Public Health Research in India***. Thus, adding the India as a limiting factor, the coverage of the work is restricted to INDIA only. Again it occurs in the mind of the researcher that Public Health Research is being carried out in India over a Century and it may not be possible to identify & collect literature so old. (It might have occurred into his/her mind that Sir Ronald Ross won Nobel Prize in 1905 for his Pioneering Research on Malaria done in Calcutta & Citation Indexing came into existence only in 1955!). So, after further trimming, the topic was modified to ***Bibliometric Analysis of Public Health Research in India: 1990 to 2005***. Here after adding the specific time period, the researcher can heave a sigh of relief as the topic has become quite workable. The researcher now faced with another problem which s/he might have not envisaged earlier. That is how s/he will proceed with the topic? S/he has to choose from the two options:

- (a) Identify some institutes doing public Health research and justify selection criteria? Or
- (b) Through searching established bibliographic databases applying requisite limiters India (as Country/Geographical area) and 1990 to 2005 (as period)?

Again, there are two important underlying issues in selecting the database.

- (i) Which of the databases to be selected? and
- (ii) Their coverage.

Let us suppose that the researcher did some background studies and settled for ***Tropical Disease Bulletin, Abstracts of Hygiene*** and the ***IMSEAR*** (Index Medicus for South East Asian Region). Accordingly, s/he further modified the topic as: ***Bibliometric Analysis of Public Health Research in India" 1990 to 2005, a study comprising three databases***. Now, the topic has been finalized and the databases were selected.

Alternately, if s/he intends to conduct studies based on specific institutes, s/he identified institutes through the ***Directory of Scientific Research Institutes of India*** and the ***NUCSS*** and finally selected top 17 institutes. Accordingly, the title of the proposed project

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modified to: *Bibliometric Analysis of Public Health Research in India-1990 to 2005: a study based on top Indian Institutes.*

It now seems clear as to how topics are selected and how the title of a project changes with change of working style.